

Universe of Opposites

Spatially multiple hypermassive black holes to white holes cosmology

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Abstract

This cosmological model considers our observable universe as part of an expanding volume, produced by an explosion inside a black hole, while other, similar, expanding volumes exist beyond our observation. Such expanding volumes emerge into the space beyond them, initially appearing there as white holes. Then, over time as they continue to expand, their matter meets up, creating contracting volumes of space that eventually form hypermassive black holes — ones containing more mass than is in the observable universe. When a tipping point is reached, such as a critical mass, these hypermassive black holes explode producing new expanding volumes. Considered at a suitably large scale, this model can be consistent with the perfect cosmological principle. This model is distinct from existing cyclical models as it has multiple explosions (big bangs) spatially spread out across the universe. It is consistent with Smoller and Temple's Shockwave Cosmology Inside a Black Hole, which integrates shockwave cosmology with general relativity to produce a universe essentially like the one we observe, including cosmological redshift and a cosmic microwave background.

Introduction

Before the discovery of galaxies and redshift in the 1920s cosmology was considered to be a part of philosophy as there was not enough data to scientifically support ideas about the large scale structure of the universe.

Cosmology nowadays has a lot of data, but that is restricted by the limits of observation. Data suggests that the universe is much larger than what we observe and may be infinite. In considering the universe beyond the observable, we are back to working without data. Here we are still doing philosophy, albeit philosophy informed by science (or what Peter Coles and Francesco Lucchin call Metacosmology).

The cosmological principle, in assuming that the universe is homogeneous with the same large scale structure as in the observable universe, is therefore a philosophical

view. Even though it may be supported by evidence from the sample of the universe that we can observe, that is not evidence for what is beyond observation.

This paper considers a model of the universe based on a different kind of homogeneity, one where a dynamic dialectical structure — with opposites such as expanding and contracting volumes — appears at a scale larger than the observable, only for homogeneity to reappear on an even larger scale.

The model proposed here is a simple one, using elements that are known from the observable universe, with the exception of the possibility that black holes might grow to a mass larger than that of the observable universe and then explode at a certain point. It provides a simple outline explanation for the origin of the 'big bang'.

A cosmological theory should seek to explain all of the data available. The standard model (Big Bang Theory) does not explain why the density of the observable universe is similar to that of a black hole, other than to consider it as a coincidence. The scientific ideas used to support this model do explain that data. Areas where those ideas need further development to explain other detailed evidence are discussed below, along with a proposed test.

Supporting ideas

This cosmological model leans heavily for support on ideas described by Smoller and Temple in Shockwave Cosmology Inside a Black Hole (<https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.1833875100>) where our observable universe is part of an expanding volume, produced by an explosion inside a black hole. The expanding volume eventually emerges as a white hole which exists only briefly and is in some ways comparable to the reverse of the formation of a black hole.

Smoller and Temple's Shockwave Cosmology has been described as producing a universe that "looks essentially identical to the aftermath of the big bang" (Luke Barnes and Geraint Lewis (2020). *The cosmic revolutionary's handbook*. Cambridge university press. pp. 215–216. ISBN 978-1-108-48670-5). So, the model is generally consistent with cosmic redshift and the cosmic microwave background, primordial nucleosynthesis and the formation of galaxies and large-scale structure. That is there is still a 'big bang' but, in this model, it is not the beginning of the entire universe, only the beginning of the expansion of one part of the universe. The model also provides an explanation for the darkness of the night sky (Olber's Paradox) as light from beyond the expanding volume has not had time to reach us yet.

However it would need further development before it could be considered as a more advantageous model than the big bang theory (or standard model) in explaining the universe. In particular it would need to explain the details of big bang nucleosynthesis, the quantitative details of the microwave background anisotropies, the Lyman-alpha forest, and galaxy surveys. (Avi Loeb quoted by Clara Moskowitz (2009-08-17). "'Big Wave' Theory Offers Alternative to Dark Energy". *Space.com*. Retrieved 2024-03-04.)

The Universe of Opposites model

As well as the expanding volume that contains our observable universe, other, similar, expanding volumes exist beyond our observation. Such expanding volumes meet up, creating contracting volumes of space that form hypermassive black holes — ones containing more mass than the observable universe. When a tipping point is reached, such as a critical mass, those hypermassive black holes explode producing new expanding volumes.

So the matter in our galaxy is on a journey from an explosion inside a black hole (the 'big bang'), will later emerge as part of a white hole and will eventually meet up with matter from expanding volumes that came from other similar explosions. It will end up as part of a hypermassive black hole, before a new cycle begins with a new explosion.

This model is distinct from existing cyclical models such as that discussed by Friedman, as it has multiple white holes (big bangs) spatially spread out across the universe.

Perfect Cosmological Principle

The model may be consistent with the perfect cosmological principle. If

considered on a sufficiently large scale, the production of expanding volumes and their merging to form contracting volumes may appear as something like a vast boiling, essentially homogeneous at all times.

Of course, it could not be ruled out that there might in fact be a tendency towards homogeneity at a sufficient scale, only for that to be overcome on an even larger scale (which might itself be overcome by homogeneity, or a tendency towards it, on a greater scale still). Within the observable universe we see homogeneity appear on the large scale. If this model is correct, that is only a tendency towards homogeneity which is overcome at the scale of the expanding volume, but homogeneity emerges again on a sufficiently large scale.

A possible test

Smoller and Temple do not set out a test for their Shockwave Cosmology idea in their paper. However, an additional concept based on it is developed by Smoller, Temple and Vogler in *An Instability of the Standard Model Creates the Anomalous Acceleration Without Dark Energy* (<https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rspa.2016.0887>). In it they propose a test for this alternative to dark energy, which, if found correct, would also indicate support for their Shockwave Cosmology. In turn this may make the Universe of Opposites model more plausible.

Suggested further research

Simulations of the model could help to understand the dynamics of the proposed expanding and contracting volumes and how they might interact.

Simulations using different average densities for the model might place a

constraint on what the actual density of a universe like the model may be. That is, above a certain density, would it be the case that we would expect to see evidence of matter from outside penetrating our observable universe, thus constraining any such universe to have a lower density of matter?

Proposed naming conventions

Hypermassive black hole has already been proposed in the title, defined as a black hole of greater mass than is in the observable universe.

Evamos: for an expanding volume, as described above. It is loosely based on the initials for an Expanding Volume of Matter and Space, but rhymed with cosmos. For the model, our observable universe would be just a part of an evamos.

Convamos: for a contracting volume, as described above.

References

Coles, Peter, and Francesco Lucchin. "Cosmology: The Origin and Evolution of Cosmic Structure." 2nd ed., Wiley, 2002.

Smoller, J., & Temple, B. (2003). Shockwave cosmology inside a black hole. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 100(20), 11216-11218. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1833875100>

Luke Barnes and Geraint Lewis (2020). *The cosmic revolutionary's handbook*. Cambridge university press. pp. 215–216. ISBN 978-1-108-48670-5

Avi Loeb quoted by Clara Moskowitz (2009-08-17). "'Big Wave' Theory Offers Alternative to Dark Energy". *Space.com*. Retrieved 2024-03-04.)

Smoller, J., Temple, B., & Vogler, Z.
(2017). An instability of the Standard
Model creates the anomalous
acceleration without dark energy.
*Proceedings of the Royal Society A:
Mathematical, Physical and
Engineering Sciences*, 473(2204),
20160887.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2016.0887>